

relative humidity [RH]) and long-term (-10 °C, 30% RH) storerooms for periodic monitoring of seed viability, and monitoring every 5 yr for the medium-term and every 10 yr for the long-term storage. These intervals follow the longevity patterns of the control varieties.

Subtropical and temperate zone varieties stored earlier were regenerated as a batch in 1973-74, before average viability dropped to 50%. Tropical varieties were rejuvenated at later intervals.

This is the longest, continuously monitored seed storage experiment on record, but the control seed lots are now running low. ■

Genetics

Combining ability of some rice cultivars with selected cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of 18 parents and the specific combining ability (SCA) of 45 crosses in a 15 (line) × 3 (tester) mating design: 12 varieties and 3 male fertility restorer lines used as pollen parents were crossed with 3 CMS lines.

The 63 treatments (15 lines, 3 testers, and 45 F₁s) were laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications during 1985 wet season under irrigation. Experimental plots were three 3-m-long rows. Row and plant spacing was kept at 20 × 15 cm. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for analysis.

Male fertility restorer line IET5656 was the best general combiner for grain yield, followed by Narendra 80, IR54, Z97 A, and T26 (Table 1). Madhuri and Sattari exhibited good GCA effect for test weight. Narendra 80 and Pankaj were good general combiners for tiller number; IR54 and T26 were good for plant height. Sattari and Narendra 80 and female line IR46829 A were good general combiners for early heading.

Table 1. General combining ability for grain yield and other characters of some parental lines.^a

Parents	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
<i>CMS female lines</i>					
V20 A	-1.54*	-0.49	0.64	-2.41**	0.28
IR46829 A	-14.48**	-2.32**	-3.78**	-2.33**	-3.75*
Z97 A	16.02**	2.82**	3.14**	-0.07	3.47**
<i>Male lines</i>					
<i>Male fertility restorer lines</i>					
IR50	3.16*	4.34**	-0.16	-2.41*	2.22**
IR54	17.12**	15.25**	4.82**	0.69	9.32**
IET5656	8.35**	8.89**	5.11**	-0.30	20.77**
<i>Non-fertility restorer varieties</i>					
Sattari	-11.90**	-15.53**	-11.77**	2.95**	-17.83**
Narendra 80	-4.20*	-3.53*	10.75**	0.57	10.73**
Pankaj	1.86	7.27**	10.29**	-0.57	-10.05**
T26	20.13**	14.25**	-2.62**	-3.47**	3.25**
Madhuri	-8.32**	-2.24	-0.16	3.26**	-8.07**

^a* and ** = significant at P.05 and P.01, respectively.

Table 2. Crosses showing specific combining ability effects for grain yield and other characters.^a

Cross	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
V20 A/IR54	26.73**	7.03*	-5.44**	1.59	-3.60*
V20 A/Sattari	-9.73**	18.08**	-3.44*	-2.45*	-2.20
IR46829 A/Pankaj	1.73	11.29**	0.11	3.96**	-3.88**
IR46829 A/Sattari	6.21	-7.62*	2.18	-0.05	8.46**
IR46829 A/T26	-15.49**	6.49	2.70	3.82**	-3.26*
Z97 A/IR50	2.95	4.59	13.64**	0.05	-5.40**
Z97 A/IET5656	4.94	-4.96	6.10**	-4.00**	23.83**

^a* and ** = significant at P. 05 and P .01, respectively.

Only seven crosses showed high SCA effects for one or more characters (Table 2). V20 A/IR54 for tall and IR46829A/T26 for dwarf plant height; IR46829 A/Sattari for early heading; IR46829 A/Pankaj and IR46829 A/T26 for test weight; 297 A/IR50 for tiller number; and Z97 A/IET5656 for grain yield were the best specific combiners.

The parental lines 297 A and IET5656 had the highest GCA effects in their respective female and male groups for grain yield, and also produced the best SCA effect for grain yield. Crosses showing high SCA effects for plant height and tiller number involved parents of high and low GCA values; parents with high GCA values exhibited high SCA effect for earlier heading date in their crosses. Parents showing high SCA values in their crosses were low general combiners for test weight. The SCA effect was more common and pro-

nounced in crosses involving male fertility restorer lines with CMS lines.

The cross combination showing high SCA effect for grain yield also showed high SCA effect for tiller number, indicating tiller number is an important yield component. ■

Relationship of genetic variances of quantitative characters in indica rice to nitrogen level

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Genetic variance reflects the magnitude of the gene effect controlling certain characters. We studied the relationship of genetic variance of 12 characters to N